

Determination of Sulphite by the Molecular Complex Formation

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Formation of a molecular complex of sulphite ion with mesitylene provides a simple and selective spectrophotometric method (λ_{\max} 305 nm) for its determination in 1.0 to 3.5 *N* sulphuric acid medium. Beer's law has been found to be obeyed for a long range 0.6–110.6 ppm of sulphite. The molar absorptivity and Sandell sensitivity values are respectively $1.3 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.06 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$. Tolerance limits of different foreign ions have been studied.

VARIOUS spectrophotometric methods have been used for analysis of sulphite ion on the basis of its reducing property¹⁻³. But the reproducibility is one of the weak aspects of this reaction. The well known method for the determination of sulphite ion is based on Schiff reaction. The colour of the reagents may be regenerated by adding formaldehyde and sulphite on bleached dye. Pararosaniline⁴ is the widely used example for this type of analysis. There are many other reagents which have been used for determination of sulphur dioxide and sulphite ion by this type of reaction⁵⁻⁸. Mercuric chloranilates have been used for the determination of sulphite⁹. Sulphur dioxide and aromatic or olefinic compounds form molecular complexes. Bhatti and Townshend¹⁰ used *o*-xylene for determination of sulphur dioxide on the basis of this molecular complex formation. In the present method, mesitylene has been used as an organic donor solvent from acidified sulphite solution and the absorbance of the molecular complex was measured.

Instability of sulphite ion in air has been a significant difficulty for its measurement. West and Gaeke⁴ used tetrachloromercurate ion for stabilising the sulphite ion, and non-toxic buffered formaldehyde absorber was used instead of toxic tetrachloromercurate¹¹. But in this work the EDTA solution which was used first by Humphrey *et al.*¹², has been used as a stabiliser for sulphite ion.

Experimental

Absorbance was measured in a Beckman 26 double beam uv-visible spectrophotometer using a pair of matched 1 cm quartz cells.

A $3.5 \times 10^{-3} M$ sodium EDTA (B.D.H.) solution was prepared in double-distilled water. A 0.2 *M* sulphite solution was prepared by dissolving sodium metabisulphite (E. Merck) in $3.5 \times 10^{-3} M$ EDTA solution. The working sulphite solution was

prepared by dilution with the EDTA solution. Sulphite was estimated titrimetrically¹³. All other chemicals used were of reagent grade. All aqueous solutions were made using double-distilled water.

Procedure: An aliquot (2 ml) of the sulphite solution (containing 79 to 3160 μg) was taken in a separatory funnel. A 9 *N* sulphuric acid (2.5 ml) was added in the solution and the solution was diluted to 10 ml with double-distilled water. Mesitylene (3 ml) was taken each time in the separatory funnel and shaken for 5 min. The organic layer was transferred to a 10 ml volumetric flask. The extraction was carried out in three batches of mesitylene. The volume of the flask was made upto the mark with mesitylene. The organic layer was dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate and the absorbance measured at 305 nm using a reagent blank.

Results

Absorbance curve and Beer's law: The absorbance values of several extracts containing known amounts of sulphite were recorded in the wavelength range 290–340 nm. In all cases reagent blanks were used as references. It was found that molecular complex had a λ_{\max} at 305 nm. Beer's law was found to be valid for solutions containing 0.6 to 110.6 μg sulphite per ml.

Effects of acid concentration and mesitylene concentration: The absorbance of the molecular complex of sulphite and mesitylene was varied with the acid concentration. The absorbance values indicated that the extraction was maximum when the acid concentration was between 1.0 to 3.5 *N* sulphuric acid. The effect of concentration of mesitylene has been observed by dilution of mesitylene with an inert solvent, *e.g.* *n*-hexane which does not form molecular complex with sulphite. The results indicate that undiluted mesitylene give the maximum absorbance.

Sensitivity of the method : The Sandell sensitivity was found to be $0.06 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$. Molar extinction coefficient and relative standard deviation was found to be $1.3 \times 10^5 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 305 nm and $\pm 1.2\%$, respectively. The confidence interval was found to be 41.0 ± 1.4 ppm sulphite for 95% confidence limit in 4 determinations.

Effect of foreign species : For the determination of 39.5 ppm sulphite by this method, the effect of various foreign ions were studied. The tolerance limits (in ppm) of different ions were as follows: Al^{III} (150), Ca^{II} (100), Cd^{II} (100), Co^{II} (100), Cu^{II} (100), Hg^{II} (100), Fe^{III} (100), Fe^{II} (50), K^{I} (200), Mn^{II} (150), Ni^{II} (100), Pb^{II} (150), Zn^{II} (100), fluoride (100), chloride (100), bromide (100), iodide (100), cyanide (100), nitrite (25), nitrate (150), phosphate (100), sulphide (100) and thiocyanate (100).

Discussion

Sulphur dioxide forms 1 : 1 molecular complexes with many aromatic hydrocarbon donors when it is absorbed by a solution of the donor in an inert solvent¹⁴. Thus formation of a 1 : 1 mesitylene-sulphur dioxide molecular complex having charge transfer absorption band at 305 nm provides a simple and selective spectrophotometric method for the determination of sulphite. EDTA, a nontoxic stabiliser, has been used in the present work. If toxic tetrachloromercurate was used for stabilisation of sulphite then bromide and iodide would interfere¹⁰. The serious interference in the pararosa-

niline⁴ method, e.g. due to nitrite, may also be avoided in this method. The great advantage of the present work is the wide range of Beer's law in comparison to other known spectrophotometric methods.

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